

Comparative analysis of seasonal Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) characterization methods and their effectiveness

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ABSTRACT

Municipal Solid waste (MSW) characterization is crucial for effective solid waste management and resource recovery. Seasonal variations significantly impact the quantity and composition of MSW, which requires specialized characterization methods to optimize waste management strategies. Numerous studies have explored different methodologies to address these seasonal changes

Seasonal variations in MSW significantly impact waste management strategies, necessitating precise characterization methods to optimize collection, treatment and disposal. This review paper examines various MSW characterization techniques, comparing traditional and advanced methodologies. Traditional methods such as physical sorting, proximate and ultimate analysis, thermo gravimetric and calorific value assessment provides direct but labor intensive insights. Advanced techniques such as spectroscopic method, Geographic Information System (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS), and Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven models, offers scalable and efficient alternatives. This paper evaluates the accuracy, cost-effectiveness, and applicability of these methods. The findings suggest that hybrid approach integrating AI, GIS and RS, and real-time monitoring could enhance waste characterization.

KEYWORDS: Thermo Gravimetric, Calorific value assessment, spectroscopic methods, Geographic Information System, Remote sensing, Artificial Intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

The economic development and industrial revolution has been significantly improved living standard of people's, leading to changes in their consumption pattern. However, these changes have also introduced considerable complexity into MSW ¹. India is a rapidly urbanizing country. The total MSW generated was about 52 million tons in the year 2016. This number is rapidly increasing with the increase in population ². MSW basically consists of mixture of household and commercial refuse generated by the residential and business communities ³.

MSW generation is a crucial environmental issue that varies significantly with seasonal changes. Seasonal changes influence waste composition due to various factors such as climate condition, tourism, festivals and change in consumption patterns ⁴. Understanding these fluctuations is much essential for designing efficient waste management strategies that align with environmental and socio economic conditions ⁵.

Accurate characterization of MSW based on seasonal variation is crucial for optimizing waste collection, segregation, and treatment processes⁶. Creating a database on waste characterization provides an opportunity to design effective waste processing and treatment system for a city⁷. Lack of sufficient data on waste characterization, financial limitations, and the presence of unskilled workers are increasing complexity in the development of MSW database⁸. The traditional methods such as manual sorting, proximate and ultimate analysis, and calorific value assessment have been widely used for management and characterization of MSW and these techniques are effective, but are often time consuming and labor intensive⁹. Manual sorting depends on human intervention to separate recyclable materials from waste, which can be prone to errors and may also leads to inconsistency¹⁰. Proximate and ultimate analysis provides information about the composition of MSW by determining parameters like moisture content, volatile matter, fixed carbon and ash content, but these methods are costly and may not always reflect the variability in waste composition^{11,12}. The energy potential of waste determined using calorific value assessment is important for waste to energy applications¹³. Despite the limitations, the traditional methods plays a crucial role in waste characterization, although there is growing shift towards advance technologies for improved efficiency and accuracy in waste management¹³.

Recent advancement in artificial intelligence (AI), remote sensing and sensor based technologies have revolutionized seasonal characterization through real time, high precision analysis, making them suitable for tracking seasonal changes in organic and recyclable waste¹⁴. Remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) approaches provides spatial insights into waste accumulation pattern across different seasons. These technologies help monitor waste generation trends and predict seasonal variations, enabling more efficient waste management solutions¹⁵.

Furthermore, AI driven technologies offers predictive analytics for seasonal waste characterization¹⁶. Machine Learning algorithms trained using historical solid waste data can accurately forecast seasonal variations, which helps waste management authorities in adjusting waste collection frequency, segregation efforts and recycling strategies¹⁷. Deep Learning algorithms enhance automated sorting, which classifies the material based on their composition, reducing human power and improving segregation efficiency¹⁸. IoT based smart waste management equipped with real time sensors can monitor seasonal fluctuations in waste disposal, which provide an aid for data driven optimization of waste collection schedules and allocation of resources¹⁹. As the urban areas experience maximum increase in waste generation, due to climatic conditions and seasonal consumption trends, use of advanced technologies in seasonal waste characterization will be crucial in developing resilient and adaptive solid waste management system²⁰.

Seasonal changes have an immense impact on composition and quantity of solid waste, festival seasons, holidays and change in climatic conditions contributes to the increase in solid waste, leading to increase burden on waste management agencies²¹. During festival seasons there will be sharp rise in food waste and kitchen waste, plastics, lightweight waste used in packaging, which challenges waste segregation and disposal practices²².

Seasonal change in weather conditions alters the moisture content and deposition rate of waste. During monsoon season due to high moisture content organic waste results in reduction of

calorific value, impacting waste-to-energy efficiency²³. Excess moisture content also accelerates microbial activity, leading to faster decomposition which increases the risk of leachate formation and landfill gases²⁴.

These seasonal changes require waste management strategies that consider both qualitative and quantities variations in waste composition. Integrating GIS, remote sensing and AI driven predictive models enables to forecast seasonal trends, optimizing waste collection routes and schedules^{20,25}. Season specific waste treatment solutions, such as increasing composition of waste during peak organic waste period, helps in improving sustainability and reduce environmental hazards²⁶.

Furthermore, effective MSW characterization plays important role in resource recovery and circular economic approaches. Local government and waste management agencies can optimize recycling programs, energy recovery processes and composting initiatives by understanding the seasonal pattern of waste²⁷. Without accurate characterization of MSW, waste treatment agencies may face inefficiencies, leading to higher operational cost.

The main aim of this study is to compare various MSW characterization methods, highlighting their effectiveness in determining seasonal trends. Through the evaluation of traditional and modern techniques, this paper provides the insights about their applicability, reliability, and efficiency for integrating modern technologies such as AI, GIS and sensor based monitoring of solid waste to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of characterization of MSW on seasonal basis.

SEASONAL VARIATIONS IN MSW

Seasonal variation in MSW composition happens due to several factors including festivals, climate change, tourism and shifting of consumption patterns. These factors lead to changes in MSW generation rates and composition across different time period and regions²⁸.

FACTORS INFLUENCING SEASONAL CHANGE IN MSW COMPOSITION

Climate: Change in weather conditions mainly influence MSW generation and composition. During monsoon season, the organic waste increases due to moisture content, which leads to faster decomposition and higher microbial activities. In the same way during dry season plastic, paper, and textile waste increases as the degradation of moisture-sensitive waste material degrade at slower rate²⁹.

Festivals and Holidays: A cultural and religious festival contributes to short term increase in MSW generation. For instance, there is notable increase in packaging waste, food and kitchen waste, wrapping papers, plastics. For this efforts must be made by the waste management agencies to generation of waste during festivals³⁰.

Tourism: Tourist destination experiences seasonal fluctuations in generation of solid waste. Coastal cities witness the increase in food and plastic waste, while resorts generate more paper and packaging waste during summer. As some food items produces higher green house gas

(GHGs) emission, managing their use in tourist spots must be limited to have eco friendly environment ³¹.

Consumption Pattern: Seasonal availability of different foodstuffs effects waste composition and generation. Food scraps accounts for greater percentage of waste generation during summer, where as there will be increase in paper and textiles in winter season due to the increased clothing usage ³².

METHODS OF MSW CHARACTERIZATION

MSW characterization is crucial for effective waste management and resource recovery. Over the years various methodologies have been developed to access generation and composition of MSW, which varies significantly with different factors. The lack of standardized methods often limit the comparability and applicability of results across different studies ^{33,34}.

TRADITIONAL METHODS

Physical sorting and manual sampling

These are the most widely used traditional techniques used in the field of MSW characterization. These methods involves direct collection, segregation and classification of solid waste which is purely based on physical properties of solid waste ³⁵. Typically waste is collected from different sources, which includes residential, commercial and industrial areas. Once the specific amount of waste is collected, manual sorting of waste is done based on the categories such as organic, paper, plastic, glass and metal ³⁶. The effectiveness of this method depends on number of samples collected, proper handling and trained personals to minimize the errors ²⁹. Physical characterization provides the data about waste composition, but this method is labor intensive and time consuming.

Furthermore, it is difficult to standardize waste characterization approach across different regions due to variation in waste generation patterns ³⁷. This method also struggles with consistency, as different researchers has classified the waste differently based on subjective judgments ^{23,29,35}. Additionally, waste collection requires planning to collect representative samples across various geographic areas and time period ³⁸. While physical sorting of waste provides the valuable baseline data, its limitations necessitate the integration of advanced techniques for improved efficiency and reliability in characterization of MSW. Composition of MSW in Crete, found that organic waste, papers and plastic accounts for 76% of total waste ³⁹. Coarsely shredded mixed commercial waste was sampled adhering to Austrian standard ONORM 2127 and the horizontal sampling standard ONORM EN 14899, this sampling procedure effectively captures the composition of mixed commercial waste ⁴⁰. Optimizing operational practices of sorting MSW and adopting modern technologies can enhance resource recovery and contributing to more effective recycling techniques ⁴¹.

Proximate and ultimate analysis

These are the chemical characterization techniques used to determine the composition of MSW, particularly focusing on their moisture content, volatile solids, fixed carbon and ash content ⁴². Proximate analysis is essential for understanding the combustibility and energy recovery potential of different waste materials, making it highly applicable for waste-to-energy applications⁴³. Ultimate analysis on the other hand deals with the determination of elemental composition, which includes carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen. These are the crucial parameters for accessing the environmental impact of incineration and combustion processes, also its contribution in energy generation ⁴⁴. Proximate analysis provides information regarding decomposition rates and biodegradability of organic waste, assisting in landfill management and composting strategies. Similarly, ultimate analysis of MSW helps in evaluating the suitability of waste in fuel production, such as refuse-derived fuel (RDF) and energy production ⁴⁵. These methods provides precise quantitative data, they requires specialized laboratory equipments and trained personnel to ensure accurate measurements. The need for rigorous sample preparation and handling is can leads to potential errors and inconsistencies ⁴⁶. Additionally, variation in composition of MSW can be due to seasonal and regional factors. The process of sampling for proximate and ultimate analysis in many research studies was carried out based on American Society of testing and materials (ASTM) ^{23,43}. Proximate analysis revealed seasonal variation in moisture content, volatile solids, fixed carbon and ash content, impacting biodegradability of the waste same way ultimate analysis determine the elemental composition of MSW resulting in variations influencing methane yield in aerobic digestion ⁴⁷. Higher volatile matter and lower ash content in MSW leads to better conversion efficiency in waste-to-energy processes for energy recovery ⁴⁸.

Thermo gravimetric (tga) and calorific value assessment

TGA is as technique used to measure thermal stability and decomposition behaviors by subjecting MSW components to controlled heating in a TGA analyzer. The weight loss of the sample is recorded as temperature, providing information about thermal degradation characteristics of different waste fractions ⁴⁹. TAG method is useful to determine the composition of biodegradable, combustible, and inert material in MSW. The results of TGA analysis is usually displayed as TGA curve in which mass is plotted against temperature ⁵⁰. TGA was carried out on plam shell solid waste which showed higher content of volatile solids, which contributes to better production of biofuel. The study highlights that the solid waste which are high in volatile solids can be used in the production of biofuel ⁵¹. Nine MSW fractions which includes food waste (orange peel and rice), paper, plastic (PE and PVC), textiles and wood through TGA analysis, the presence of plastic tends to increase overall heat required for pyrolysis ⁵². The diverse composition of MSW leads to varying thermal degradation behaviors among its components. Pyrolysis characteristics and kinetics of MSW are crucial and also depends on several factors, which includes material decomposition, heating rate, and operational conditions. Comprehensive studies using techniques like TGA are essential to develop efficient and sustainable pyrolysis processes for waste management and resource recovery ⁵³. TGA under non-isothermal conditions analyze the composition of waste-derived-fuels such as solid recovered fuels (SRF) and refuse-derived fuel (RDF) by determining thermal behavior of various

components⁵⁴. TGA are very helpful in predicting the combustion dynamics and waste-to-energy processes and confirms that MSW and RDF can serve as a sustainable fuel⁵⁵.

Calorific value assessment, measures the energy content of solid waste using bomb calorimeter²³. The calorific value provides a direct indicator for energy recovery of MSW, making it essential fact in waste management studies. MSW in Enugu has a significant calorific value of approximately 5.66 billion Kilo Joules per day, translating to 1.57 million kWh of electricity generation, offering a sustainable waste-to-energy solution⁵⁶. Some solid waste incineration burns waste that does not provides enough calorific required for the energy generation, hence calorific value must be determined before waste treatment process⁵⁷. Organic fraction of MSW has a substantial calorific value, making it viable for energy recovery⁵⁸.

ADVANCED METHODS

Spectroscopic and chromatographic method

These method are the combined analytical techniques where chromatography is used to separate the components of mixture and spectroscopy is used to identify and quantify each separated components, providing detailed insights about the chemical structure and composition of MSW⁵⁹.

Spectroscopic method

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) is a advanced technique used in MSW characterization, provides insights about the chemistry of materials proving to be the appropriate tool for quality control for assessment of abandoned landfills⁶⁰. Spectroscopic techniques can effectively monitor the degradation and stabilization of organic compounds⁶¹. FTIR spectroscopy, when paired with multivariate data analysis techniques a like principal component analysis (PCA) and soft independent modeling of class analogy (SIMCA) can effectively classify solid waste material based on their composition⁶². FTIR spectroscopy method was used to investigate the stability and composition of compost extract, findings indicate that extracts derived from composts exhibits consistent chemical profile⁶³. FTIR identifies distinct indicator bands corresponding to various stages of organic matter degradation and acts as valuable tool for monitoring biological stability of MSW⁶⁴. While investigating the composting process of MSW using FTIR revealed that compost produced during summer and spring exhibits high molecular complexity and stability compared to winter, which suggest that seasonal variation in temperature significantly influence the composting efficiency⁶⁵.

Chromatographic method

Gas Chromatography – mass spectroscopy (GC – MS) is a advanced analytical technique employed for MSW characterization at molecular level⁶⁶. They provides highly specific results, making it a preferred choice for identifying contaminants and pollutants in MSW⁶⁷. Monitoring specific Volatile Organic compounds (VOC) can be effectively managed using GC – MS⁶⁸. Organic solvents and water extract from fly ash was analyzed using injection – gas chromatography – mass spectroscopy with programmable temperature vaporizer, detected over

100 compounds in organic solvent extract ⁶⁹. Thirty three physiochemical samples which were collected monthly for eight months, Solid phase Microextraction (SPME) coupled with GC – MS was employed to identify organic pollutants ⁷⁰. The optimized microwave assisted extraction techniques, followed by GC – MS analysis adopted to extract and quantify 16 polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and 14 polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) was helpful in assessing organic micro pollutant contamination in biowaste, supporting resource recovery within a circular economy framework ⁷¹.

Remote sensing (RS) and geographic information system (GIS)

RS and GIS technologies have revolutionized MSW characterization by enabling large scale spatial analysis of waste generation, composition and disposal pattern ⁷². Earth observation satellites, equipped with advanced sensor and imaging capabilities, has been providing data for several decades, facilitating the development of specialized technique to perform task such as waste site detection, monitoring of dumping activities and in landfill site selection ⁷³. Remote sensing data along with geological and geophysical data can be utilized for qualitative and quantitative characterization of MSW in uncontrolled dumpsites and landfills ⁷⁴. Integration of remote sensing techniques with ground based geophysical methods can be used to locate and assess and abandoned MSW landfill in French Western Alps, by analyzing historical aerial photographs and LiDAR data ⁷⁵. Utilizing Sentinel 2 satellite imagery and Digital Elevation Model (DEM), the researchers were able to access and manage MSW in Najran city ⁷⁶. Land surface temperature (LST) and various vegetative indexes derived from Landsat 8, to assess the bio thermal effects of MSW dumping, it revealed that MSW dump exhibits an average increase in temperature of 4.3K compared to nearby agricultural land and 2.78K compared to urban areas ⁷⁷. Hyperspectral Imaging and big data analytics enables precise material identification, facilitating improved waste segregation and resource recovery ⁷⁸. Multispectral aircraft and satellite system analyzes both spectral and physical characteristics of hazardous waste, which enhances the accuracy of waste identification ⁷⁹.

GIS has the ability to produce thematic maps that simplifies the interpretation of waste generation and composition patterns ⁸⁰. Integration of waste characterization with GIS reveals that organic waste forms a major portion of MSW, suggesting that composting initiatives can help convert it into useful fertilizer; also GIS based assessment successfully identifies suitable sites for waste disposal ⁸¹. GIS models helps in optimizing waste collection routes, identifying suitable location for waste treatment facilities and predict waste generation based on urban growth ⁸². A case study of the city of Gutineau demonstrates the application of GIS, which focuses on creating models of MSW generation based on socioeconomic and demographic factors, resulting in accurately predicting quality and quantity of waste streams ⁸³. Socioeconomic factors, particularly family size and education level, significantly influence household solid waste generation rates, the applicability of GIS along with Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) successfully identifies suitable landfill locations ⁸⁴. (Table 1) provides summary of some recent studies, where GIS and RS are used as the advanced techniques in MSW characterization.

Table 1**A Summary on recent studies that adopted GIS and RS for MSW characterization**

Satellite data used in study	Objectives	Key Findings	References
Multispectral Image	To characterize spectral reflectance of various plastic and organic waste types	Multispectral image combined with advance data analysis technique like PCA can act as a powerful tool for identification and classification of different waste materials	85
Multispectral Imagery (Sentinel - 2)	To detect and map plastic waste on land surface	Maximum likelihood classification and Support Vector classification was applied on Sentinel – 2 imagery. Bands 6, 7 and 8 of this imagery exhibits higher spectral reflectance for plastic materials. The study suggests that supervised classification can be used to detect plastic waste.	86
Hyperspectral Imagery	Identification of various MSW components	Combination of Hyperspectral Imaging with machine learning models offers a promising approach for MSW characterization by demonstrating strong predictive capabilities for chemical properties of the waste materials.	87
Hyperspectral Imagery	Sorting of plastic from Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipments using Hyperspectral Imaging in Short Wave InfraRed range (SWIR)	Findings suggest that HIS combined with chemometric techniques, offers user friendly method of material characterization, quality control and sorting in recycling technique.	88
Near InfraRed (NIR) Hyperspectral Imagery	The study aims to develop rapid and reliable method for identifying and separating polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	NIR Hyperspectral Imaging proves to be promising tool for effective separation of PET and PVC.	89
Hyperspectral Remote Sensing with	To detect and characterize solid waste materials at sub	This approach facilitated the identification of various waste materials that are often challenging to detect	90

spectral unimixing techniques	pixels level using hyperspectral Imagery	using traditional remote sensing method due to their mixed nature within individual pixels	
Thermal InfraRed Imagery	The study aims to develop an explicit equation that predicts methane (CH ₄) emission based on ground temperature anomalies	Thermal InfraRed Imagery enhances the detection and quantification of methane emission from landfills.	91,92

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

AI is transforming MSW management by introducing advanced methods for effective waste classification⁹³. Traditional waste sorting methods are basically labor intensive and are prone to errors, leading to inefficient recycling processes and environmental errors⁹⁴. The applications of AI and machine learning (ML) allows for more accurate analysis and forecasting waste generation trends, leading to better understanding and characterization of MSW^{94,95}. AI driven framework has been proposed for MSW classification, these framework incorporate intelligent recognition, management strategies and AI based technologies to modernize waste classification services⁹⁶. A novel method predicts and classify decomposable and non decomposable waste by integrating IoT based analysis with AI, leading to improved waste segregation⁹⁷. A study introduced a innovative waste classification system combining feature extraction, helps in achieving high accuracy in waste material characterization⁹⁴. Research has been carried out on developing smart system that automatically detect and classify waste materials, by reducing the limitation of manual sorting⁹⁸. AI powered mobile application assist users in accurately disposing solid waste. For example, “DeepWaste” application utilizes AI techniques to classify waste into categories like trash, recycling and composting⁹⁹. Smart bins equipped with sensors recognizes the waste materials such as plastic, glass and metals, they can streamline the recycling process and helps in reducing the waste sent to landfills¹⁹. (Table 2) provides information regarding various AI technologies utilized in classification of MSW.

Table 2

Some Applications of AI technologies in waste sorting

Field	Key Information	References
AI powered waste classification using Convolution Neural Network (CNN)	Researchers have developed AI model utilizing CNN to classify the MSW effectively. These models analyze image of waste items and categorize them into appropriate classes. CNN are capable of learning and identifying patterns in waste image.	100–105
Smart bins with edge AI capabilities	Smart bind equipped with AI models deployed on edge device automatically	106–110

	classifies waste into categories such as plastic, glass, metal and paper. Some are Bin-e, Enevo Smart Bin, TrashBot, Cleo AI Bin	
Mobile Application for waste sorting	It employs deep learning techniques to assist user in correctly disposing of waste, by classifying the waste into trash, plastic, paper, metal, glass or cardboard. Some mobile applications are DeepWaste, MWaste, MobileNet.	99,111-114
AI in waste detection for Environmental Cleanup	Here AI is used to detect waste in natural environment, where it detects and classify litter, where basically neural network is used.	115-117
AI Application in Waste-to-energy processes	AI has been applied in waste-to-energy processes, optimizing the conversion of waste materials into energy. AI combined with chemical analysis improves carbon emission estimation, waste pyrolysis and energy conversion.	118-120, 20
Deep learning for Organic waste sorting	The integration of deep learning with waste sorting provides a sustainable and scalable approach to waste management. The hybrid deep learning model integrating CNN achieved 96.78% accuracy, surpassing traditional models and enhancing intelligent waste classification. Eco Cycle Classifier Deep Neural Network (ECCDN) – Net performed state-of-art models, attaining 96.10% classification accuracy. A robust deep learning classification approach introduced a dual stream network and (Generalized Efficient Layer Aggregation Network) GELAN-E object detection, improving classification and sorting efficiency.	121-123

COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT MSW CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

In (Table 3) the comparison of traditional and advanced methods has been highlighted based on accuracy, cost and time efficiency, scalability and seasonal variation detection of MSW.

Table 3

Comparison of various traditional and advanced methods in MSW characterization

Method	Accuracy	Cost	Time	Scalability	Seasonal
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			Efficiency		Variation Detection
Physical Sorting and Manual Sampling	Moderate	Low	Low	Low	Limited trend detection and labor intensive
Proximate and Ultimate analysis	High	High	Low	Moderate	Organic and Inorganic compositional shift
TGA	Very High	High	Moderate	Low	Thermal stability and decomposition patterns
Calorific Value Assessment	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Energy Potential variation
Spectroscopy	Very High	Very High	Low	Low	Chemical compositional variation
GIS and RS	High	Moderate	High	High	Spatial and temporal waste distribution.
AI-based	High	Moderate	High	High	Automated detection and prediction along with real-time seasonal variation of MSW

FUTURE DIRECTION AND RECOMMENDATION

The field of seasonal MSW characterization is evolving, with advancements in RS and GIS, AI and spectroscopy than traditional methods, offering modern techniques for improving waste analysis and management. One of the most promising directions is the integration of AI and IoT based smart sensors, which enables real time monitoring of waste composition and seasonal trends forecasting. The use of ML and DL algorithms along with sensor based data can optimize waste collection schedules and enhance predictive modeling for seasonal variations.

Another important are is Spectroscopic and chromatographic techniques, which provides high resolution waste composition data with minimal sample preparation. Future research should focus on developing portable and cost effective spectroscopic sensors to enable on-site MSW

characterization. Similarly, the application of GIS and RS, which includes multispectral, hyperspectral and thermal remote sensing, can help map seasonal waste generation hotspots. Establishing GIS-based decision support system (DSS) can facilitate effective and efficient waste collection route optimization and helps in strategic waste disposal.

Significant challenges in MSW characterization is the lack of standardized methodologies across studies, leading to inconsistencies in data interpretation. Future efforts should focus on developing a framework for standardized seasonal waste analysis, integrating thermal, calorific and elemental analysis for more uniform and comparable approach. Additionally, AI driven predictive models have the potential to waste trends accurately by analyzing historical waste data, climate variables and socioeconomic factors. Deploying DL and reinforced learning algorithms can dynamically adjust waste collection and treatment strategies based on seasonal variations.

Seasonal variation in MSW affects the efficiency of waste-to-energy processes, composting and anaerobic digestion. Conducting life cycle assessments (LCA) can help optimize the conversion of seasonal waste fractions into biofuels and other valuable byproducts. Lastly, policy and regulatory frameworks need to be upgraded with AI and IoT-driven waste management solutions. By the utilization AI-based models, the field of seasonal MSW characterization can transit towards data-driven, technology-enabled and sustainable waste management system, ensuring better environment and economic outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Seasonal MSW characterization is a critical component of effective waste management. This review paper highlights the diverse methodologies used in the field of waste characterization, from physical sorting to advanced spectroscopy, GIS and RS and AI-driven approaches. Each method offer unique strength and limitations, particularly in terms of accuracy, cost, time efficiency, and scalability. However, the advancement in MSW characterization can be achieved by the integration of IoT based smart sensor with AI, enabling real-time monitoring and predictive modeling for seasonal waste trends. Additionally, the application of GIS and RS can enhance the ability to map and manage waste on a spatial and temporal scale.

To maintain standardization in MSW characterization methods the development of portable spectroscopic sensors and AI-powered waste management system proves to be the exciting opportunities for both academic research and practical applications in waste management. Furthermore, improving sustainability through the optimization of waste-to-energy processes and biofuel production will be important for addressing the challenges posed by seasonal variations in waste composition.

Ultimately, a holistic approach, integrating cutting-edge technologies, policy framework, and sustainable waste treatment strategies, will pave the way for sustainable waste management system. The recommendations presented in this paper provides a roadmap for future research and implementation, with the potential to significantly enhance our understanding of seasonal waste changes and improve the overall efficiency in MSW management strategies.

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